

Synthesis of 2-aryl-3-(*N*⁹-carbazolylacetamidyl)-4-oxothiazolidines and their 5-arylidenes as antifungal and analgesic agents

S. K. Srivastava*, S. Srivastava and S. D. Srivastava

Synthetic Organic Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, India

Manuscript received 17 July 2000, revised 30 October 2000, accepted 26 December 2000

Several 2-aryl-3-(*N*⁹-carbazolylacetamidyl)-4-oxothiazolidines (4) and 2-aryl-3-(*N*⁹-carbazolylacetamidyl)-5-arylidene-4-oxothiazolidines (5) have been synthesised and tested for their antifungal and analgesic activities.

Carbazole derivatives possess a broad spectrum of biological activities¹. The incorporation of 4-oxothiazolidines and their 5-arylidene derivatives in carbazole nucleus through acyl bridge has been found to enhance their biological activities². In view of these, we have synthesised some 4-oxothiazolidines that have been linked with carbazoles *N*⁹-position through an acetamidyl bridge and evaluate their biological properties.

Carbazole upon reaction with ethyl chloroacetate in presence of K₂CO₃ yielded ethyl *N*⁹-carbazolylacetate (1). The latter in a reaction with hydrazine hydrate was converted into *N*⁹-carbazolylacetylhydrazine (2) which on condensation with various aromatic aldehydes gave the corresponding arylidene derivative (3). Refluxation of 3 with mercaptoacetic acid gave 2-aryl-3-(*N*⁹-carbazolylacetamidyl)-4-oxothiazolidines (4) which upon Knoevengel reaction with various aromatic aldehydes afforded the 2-aryl-3-(*N*⁹-carbazolylacetamidyl)-5-arylidene-4-oxothiazolidines (5) (Scheme 1).

Compounds 4 and 5 were screened for their antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* (*C.a.*), *Rizopus oryzae* (*R.o.*), *Aspergillus niger* (*A.n.*) and *Cryosporium ponnical* (*C.p.*) at 100 and 500 ppm concentrations using griseofulvin and dithane (M-45) as standards. Compounds with pronounced activity are as follows: 4c, 5c against *R.o.*, 4d, 5d against *R.o.* and *C.p.*, 4e, 5a, 5e against *A.n.*, 4f against *C.p.*, 4g against *C.a.* and *C.p.* and 5g against *C.a.*, *R.o.* and *C.p.*

Compounds 4 and 5 were tested for their analgesic activity in albino rats (80–110 g) by the reported method³ (intraperitoneally at a dose 100 mg/kg b.w.) using acetylsalicylic acid (i.p. 50 mg/kg b.w., PAS 213.23%) as standard. Compounds 4g, 4h, 4i, 5g, 5h and 5i showed 155.88, 158.77, 164.06, 194.20, 181.42 and 189.55% analgesic activity, respectively in comparison to the standard 213.23%. 320

3, 4 a	Ar ¹ = 2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	f	Ar ¹ = 4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄
b	Ar ¹ = 3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	g	Ar ¹ = 2-Br.C ₆ H ₄
c	Ar ¹ = 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	h	Ar ¹ = 3-Br.C ₆ H ₄
d	Ar ¹ = 2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	i	Ar ¹ = 4-Br.C ₆ H ₄
e	Ar ¹ = 3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄		
5a	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	f	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄
b	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	g	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 2-Br.C ₆ H ₄
c	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	h	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 3-Br.C ₆ H ₄
d	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	i	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 4-Br.C ₆ H ₄
e	Ar ¹ = Ar ² = 3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄		

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) NH₂NH₂ (ii) Ar¹ CHO, (iii) mercaptoacetic acid, THF, (iv) Ar² CHO, C₂H₅ONa.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201

Note

PC spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra on a Bruker DRX spectrometer (200 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. All compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Ethyl N⁹-carbazolylacetate (1): A mixture of carbazole (0.1 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) and of anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4 g) in dry Me_2CO (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 13 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to get a solid substance which was dissolved in CHCl_3 and passed through a column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol (4 : 6, v/v) as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product crystallised from ethanol, (85%), m.p. 85–87° (Found : C, 75.82; H, 5.90; N, 5.50. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$ requires : C, 75.88; H, 5.92; N, 5.53%); ν_{max} 1725 (C=O ester), 1460 cm^{-1} (N-CH₂); δ 1.20 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.08 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.55 (2H, s, N-CH₂) and 7.20–7.85 (8H, m, ArH).

N⁹-Carbazolylacetyl hydrazine (2): A mixture of **1** (0.08 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.08 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h, then cooled and the solvent removed to get a solid product which was dissolved in CHCl_3 and passed through a column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol (5 : 5, v/v) as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was recrystallised from methanol, (82%), m.p. 85–86° (Found : C, 70.22; H, 5.43; N, 17.50. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires : C, 70.29; H, 5.43; N, 17.57%); ν_{max} 3350 (NHNH₂), 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O amido); δ 3.60 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.40 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.15–7.80 (8H, m, ArH) and 7.88 (1H, s, CONH).

N⁹-(Arylidenehydrazidomethyl)carbazole (3a): A mixture of **2** (0.05 mol) in CHCl_3 (30 ml), 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.05 mol) and 4–5 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The solvent was then removed to obtain a residue which was dissolved in benzene and passed through a column of silica gel using benzene : methanol (6 : 4, v/v) mixture as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product crystallized from ethanol, (82%), m.p. 107–108° (Found : C, 69.68; H, 4.40; N, 11.59. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}_3\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 69.70; H, 4.42; N, 11.61%); ν_{max} 3335 (NH), 1655 cm^{-1} (C=O amido); δ 3.65 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.35 (1H, s, N=CH), 7.10–7.90 (12H, m, ArH) and 8.05 (1H, s, CONH).

Likewise, **3b-i** were prepared by treating **2** with various aromatic aldehydes : **3b** (81%), m.p. 118–120°, ν_{max} 3330, 1655 cm^{-1} ; **c** (80%), 114–115°, ν_{max} 3330, 1650 cm^{-1} ; **d** (75%), 128–129°, ν_{max} 3330, 1660 cm^{-1} , δ 3.60 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.30 (1H, s, N=CH), 7.10–8.00 (12H, m, ArH), 8.10 (1H, s, CONH); **e** (78%), 140–141°, ν_{max} 3330, 1650 cm^{-1} ; **f** (70%), 150–152°, ν_{max} 3340, 1660 cm^{-1} ; **g** (79%), 160–161°, ν_{max} 3335, 1660 cm^{-1} , δ 3.65 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.35

(1H, s, N=CH), 7.00–7.90 (12H, m, ArH), 8.05 (1H, s, CONH); **h**, (82%), 158–159°, ν_{max} 3335, 1660 cm^{-1} ; **i** (78%), m.p. 163–165°, ν_{max} 3330, 1650 cm^{-1} .

2-(Substituted-aryl)-3-(N⁹-carbazolylacetamidyl)-4-oxo-thiazolidines (4a): A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) in THF (30 ml) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.01 mol) with a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl_2 was refluxed for 12 h on a water-bath. The solvent was then removed to get a residue which was dissolved in benzene and passed through a column of silica gel using benzene : chloroform (8 : 2, v/v) mixture as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product crystallised from methanol, (76%), m.p. 126–128° (Found : C, 63.31; H, 4.10; N, 9.62. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$ requires : C, 63.37; H, 4.13; N, 9.64%); ν_{max} 3340 (NH), 1715 (C=O cyclic), 1660 cm^{-1} (C=O amido); δ 3.15 (1H, s, CH-N), 3.60 (2H, s, CH₂-S), 3.72 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 7.10–7.80 (12H, m, ArH), 8.60 (1H, s, CONH).

Similarly, **4b-i** were prepared from **3b-i** using different aromatic aldehydes : **4b** (72%), m.p. 124–126°, ν_{max} 3340, 1710, 1665 cm^{-1} ; **c** (75%), 128–129°, ν_{max} 3335, 1710, 1660 cm^{-1} ; **d** (68%), 140–142°, ν_{max} 3340, 1715, 1660 cm^{-1} , δ 3.10 (1H, s, CH-N), 3.65 (2H, s, CH₂-S), 3.75 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 7.00–8.00 (12H, m, ArH), 8.65 (1H, s, CONH); **e** (70%), 155–156°, ν_{max} 3340, 1715, 1660 cm^{-1} ; **f** (66%), 170–171°, ν_{max} 3345, 1715, 1660 cm^{-1} ; **g** (76%), 168–169°, ν_{max} 3350, 1715, 1655 cm^{-1} , δ 3.15 (1H, s, CH-N), 3.60 (2H, s, CH₂-S), 3.70 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 7.10–8.00 (12H, m, ArH), 8.60 (1H, s, CONH); **h** (78%), 171–172°, ν_{max} 3340, 1720, 1660 cm^{-1} ; **i** (73%), 174–175°, ν_{max} 3340, 1715, 1655 cm^{-1} .

2-(Substituted-aryl)-3-(N⁹-carbazolylacetamidyl)-5-arylidene-4-oxo-thiazolidines (5a): A mixture of **4a** (0.005 mol) and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.005 mol) in dioxane (40 ml) in the presence of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ONa}$ was refluxed for 6 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to get a solid which was filtered and dried. It was then dissolved in CHCl_3 and purified over the column of silica gel using benzene : methanol (8 : 2, v/v) mixture as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product crystallised from ethanol (73%), m.p. 140–141° (Found : C, 64.49; H, 3.73; N, 7.50. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{SCl}_2$ requires : C, 64.51; H, 3.76; N, 7.52%); ν_{max} 3350 (NH), 1710 (C=O cyclic), 1650 (C=O amido), 1630 cm^{-1} (C=CHAR); δ 3.20 (1H, s, CH-N), 3.70 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 5.15 (1H, s, C=CHAR), 8.50 (1H, s, CONH), 7.10–8.00 (16H, m, ArH).

Similarly, **5b-i** were prepared from **4b-i** : **5b** (74%), m.p. 132–133°, ν_{max} 3345, 1710, 1655, 1625 cm^{-1} ; **c** (68%), 140–142°, ν_{max} 3350, 1715, 1655, 1630 cm^{-1} ; **d** (76%), 158–159°, ν_{max} 3340, 1710, 1660, 1625 cm^{-1} , δ 3.20 (1H, s, -CH-N), 3.70 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 5.25 (1H, s, C=CHAR), 7.00–

8.20 (16H, m, ArH), 8.50 (1H, s, CONH); **e** (70%), 160–162°, ν_{\max} 3345, 1715, 1660, 1630 cm^{-1} ; **f** (68%), 180–181°, ν_{\max} 3350, 1715, 1660, 1630 cm^{-1} ; **g** (76%), 178–179°, ν_{\max} 3340, 1720, 1660, 1630 cm^{-1} , δ 3.15 (1H, s, CH-N), 3.75 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 5.05 (1H, s, C=CHAr), 7.00–8.00 (12H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, s, CONH); **h** (72%), 190–191°, ν_{\max} 3350, 1720, 1660, 1630 cm^{-1} ; **i** (72%), 198–199°, ν_{\max} 3345, 1715, 1650, 1630 cm^{-1} .

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Head, R S I C., C.D R I., Lucknow for providing spectral and analytical data. One of the authors (S.S.) is thankful to state U G C., Bhopal for providing a Teachers Research Fellowship.

References

- 1 S K Srivastava, S Srivastava and S D Srivastava, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1999, **38**, 183
- 2 H Wamhoff, "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", 1984, Pergamon, New York, 1984, A R Katritzky, "Hand Book of Heterocyclic Chemistry", Pergamon, New York, 1985, R S Lodhi and S D Srivastava, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1997, **36**, 947, P K Jain and S K Srivastava, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1990, **67**, 775, 1992, **69**, 403, Y K Shukla and S D Srivastava, *Indian J Chem Sect B*, 1994, **33**, 397, *Indian J Pharm Sci*, 1994, **56**, 30, D P Chakraborty, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1989, **66**, 843, T R Radhakrishnan, *Indian J Heterocycl Chem*, 1995, **5**, 1933
- 3 N B Eddy and D J Leimbach, *J Pharm Expt Thera*, 1953, **107**, 385, M Mishra, S K Srivastava and S D Srivastava, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1997, **36**, 826